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Research Article

Formulation And Evaluation Of Etoposide Liposomal Drug Delivery System

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ABSTRACT

In the present work an attempt is being made to provide for stable drug delivery system with or having improved therapeutic index for Etoposide in form of lyophilized liposomes. Liposomes have been loaded by Etoposide as a model drug using thin film hydration technique for targeted delivery of this drug. Etoposide containing liposomes with an encapsulation efficiency of 84.69 % were prepared, and the in vitro release of Etoposide from the liposomes complied with a first-order kinetic equation. In conclusion, the formulation was optimized, the prepared liposomes had a high Etoposide encapsulation rate and good reproducibility, and there in vitro release had a certain delayed-release effect.

INTRODUCTION

Novel Drug Delivery System (NDDS) fulfils desirable characteristics that it should deliver drug at a rate directed by need of body, over period of treatment & should channel active entity at site of action. Conventional dosage forms including prolonged released dosage forms unable to fulfilled none of these desired characteristics.¹ Vesicles have become the vehicle of choice in drug

delivery system called Vesicular Drug Delivery System.”, e.g. liposomes, Niosomes, Pharmacosomes etc.² Liposomes are small artificial vesicles of spherical shape that can be created from cholesterol and natural non-toxic phospholipids. Due to their size and hydrophobic and hydrophilic character(besides biocompatibility), liposomes are promising systems for drug delivery.³ “Liposome is simple

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microscopic vesicles in which an aqueous volume is entirely enclosed by a membrane composed of lipid molecule.⁴ Etoposide (ETP) is an antineoplastic agent, which acts by forming a ternary complex with topoisomerase II and DNA, causing DNA breaks and cell death. It is part of the first line therapy for small cell lung carcinoma and drug-resistant testicular cancer. However, strong lipophilicity is a major limitation in the administration of ETP, and vehicles needed as solubilizers have often been associated with adverse effects.⁵

MATERIALS

Etoposide was obtained from Alkem Pvt Mumbai, Cholesterol and Phosphatidylcholine procured from SD fine chemicals Mumbai. Other chemicals and the reagents used were of analytical grade.

METHODOLOGY

Preparation of Liposomes

Liposomes were prepared by physical dispersion method using different ratio of lipids. In this

method the lipids were dissolved in chloroform. This solution of lipids in chloroform was spread over flat bottom conical flask. The solution was then evaporated at room temperature without disturbing the solution. The hydration of lipid film form was carried out with aqueous medium phosphate buffer (pH 7.4). For this the flask was inclined to one side and aqueous medium containing drug to be entrapped was introduced down the side of flask and flask was slowly returned to upright orientation. The fluid was allowed to run gently over lipid layer and flask was allowed to stand for 2 h at 37°C for complete swelling. After swelling, vesicles are harvested by swirling the contents of flask to yield milky white suspension. Then formulations were subjected to centrifugation. Different batches of liposomes were prepared in order to select an optimum formula. All batches of liposomes were prepared as per the general method described above.⁶

Table-1: Composition of Lipids for Preparation of Liposome

Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8
Phosphatidylcholine	100	200	300	400	500	600	700	800
Cholesterol	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Solvent(Chloroform)	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Drug	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
Phosphate buffer pH 7.4	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10

Evaluations of Liposomes

Drug Entrapment Efficiency of Liposomes

Entrapment efficiency of liposomes was determined by centrifugation method. Aliquots (1 ml) of liposomal dispersion were subjected to centrifugation on a laboratory centrifuge (Remi R4C) at 3500 rpm for a period of 90 min. The clear supernatants were removed carefully to separate non-entrapped Etoposide and absorbance recorded at 245nm. The sediment in the centrifugation tube was diluted to 100 ml with phosphate buffer pH 7.4 and the absorbance of this solution was recorded at 245nm.⁷

Amount of Etoposide in supernatant and sediment gave a total amount of Etoposide in 1 ml dispersion.

% entrapment of drug was calculated by the following formula

$$\% \text{ Drug Entrapped (PDE)} = \frac{\text{Amount of Drug in Sediment}}{\text{Total Amount of Drug}} \times 100$$

Particle Size Analysis

All the prepared batches of liposomes were viewed under microscope to study their size. Size of liposomal vesicles from each batch was measured at different location on slide by taking a small drop

of liposomal dispersion on it and average size of liposomal vesicles were determined.⁸

SEM Analysis

The morphology of liposomes was studied by a scanning electron microscope. For this purpose, the sample was lyophilized and placed on aluminium stubs and the surface was coated with a layer of gold particles using a sputter coater. The shape of the liposomes was determined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) (XL30, Philips, the Netherlands) at 15 kV and 750mA.⁹

Zeta Potential (ZP)

Zeta potential (ZP) is a physical property that controls electrostatic interactions in particle dispersions and is essential in understanding the stability of colloidal dispersions. It is identified as the difference in potential between the particle and its ionic atmosphere surrounding the medium and is measured in the plane of shear. A ZP value of ± 30 mV is generally chosen to deduce particle stability, with an absolute value greater than 30 mV designated a stable condition, whereas a low zeta potential value of less than 30 mV indicates a condition toward aggregation, instability, flocculation, or coagulation. There are many factors affecting the stability of wound-dressing materials, including pH, temperature, instability radiation, concentration, the ionic strength of the solution, and the nature of the surface ligands.¹⁰

In Vitro Drug Release Study

The release studies were carried out in 10 ml Franz diffusion cell containing 10 ml Phosphate buffer. Phosphate buffer pH 7.4 (10ml) was placed in a 10 ml beaker. The beaker was assembled on a magnetic stirrer and the medium was equilibrated at $37 \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$. Dialysis membrane was taken and one end of the membrane was sealed. After separation of non-entrapped Etoposide liposomal dispersion was filled in the dialysis membrane and other end was closed. The dialysis membrane containing the sample was suspended in the medium. 1smL of

aliquots were withdrawn at specific intervals, filtered after withdrawal and the apparatus was immediately replenished with same quantity of fresh buffer medium.¹¹

Drug Release Kinetics

The models used were zero order (equation 1) First order (equation 2) and Higuchi model (equation 3) and Korsmeyer Peppas model (equation 4).

i) Zero Order Kinetics:

$$R = K_0 t \quad \text{-- (1)}$$

R=cumulative percent drug

K_0 =zero order rate constant

ii) First Order Kinetics

$$\log C = \log C_0 - K_1 t / 2.303 \quad \text{-- (2)}$$

Where C = cumulative percent drug

K_1 = first order rate constant

iii) Higuchi Model

$$R = K_H t^{0.5} \quad \text{-- (3)}$$

Where R = cumulative percent drug

K_H = higuchi model rate constant

iv) Korsmeyer Peppas Model:

$$M_t / M_\infty = K_k t^n$$

$$\log M_t / M_\infty = \log K_k + n \log t \quad \text{-- (4)}$$

Where K_k = Korsmeyer Peppas rate constant

' M_t / M_∞ ' is the fractional drug, n = diffusional exponent, which characterizes the mechanism of drug. The obtained regression co-efficient (which neared 0.999) was used to understand the pattern of the drug from the Liposomes.¹²

Stability Studies:

The success of an effective formulation can be evaluated only through stability studies. The purpose of stability testing is to obtain a stable product which assures its safety and efficacy up to the end of shelf life at defined storage conditions and peak profile. The prepared Etoposide liposomes were placed on plastic tubes containing desiccant and stored at ambient conditions, such as at room temperature, $40 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and refrigerator $2-8^\circ\text{C}$ for a period of 90 days.¹³

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Drug-Excipient Compatibility Studies (FT-IR)

The compatibility between the drug and the selected lipid and other excipients was evaluated using FTIR peak matching method. There was no appearance or disappearance of peaks in the drug-

lipid mixture, which confirmed the absence of any chemical interaction between the drug, lipid and other chemicals.

Fig-1: FTIR Analysis of Drug

Fig-2: FTIR Analysis of Optimized Formulation

Particle Size

Vesicle Shape: Vesicle shape of the prepared formulation was found to be spherical from the SEM (scanning electron microscope) analysis at 15.00kV.

Vesicle Size:

Fig-3: Particle Size of Etoposide Liposomes

SEM Analysis

Fig-4: SEM Analysis of Etoposide Liposomes

Table-2: Mean Particle Size (mps) of Different Formulation of Liposomes

Sr. No.	Formulation No.	Particle Size (nm)
1	F1	98
2	F2	96
3	F3	85
4	F4	72
5	F5	99
6	F6	80
7	F7	93
8	F8	97

Drug Entrapment Efficiency

Table- 3: Different Batches of Liposome Made By Using Different Ratio of Lipids

Formulation No.	DEE
F1	79.81
F2	80.20
F3	76.84
F4	83.46
F5	75.98
F6	84.69
F7	80.32
F8	82.21

Drug Release Studies

Table-4: Cumulative Percentage Drug Release from Various Formulations of Liposomes

Time	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	14.69	13.65	15.20	14.93	14.93	15.11	13.96	12.52
2	25.80	26.90	28.91	25.42	24.76	25.98	24.93	22.95
3	30.25	35.86	36.97	35.90	34.52	33.32	36.51	35.32

4	46.98	45.90	44.84	45.89	46.98	49.78	48.93	46.89
5	57.81	55.82	56.93	58.93	57.60	59.10	58.76	55.57
6	63.92	65.91	64.88	65.89	64.90	65.98	64.82	65.98
7	73.58	74.90	76.93	73.90	76.85	80.24	79.81	83.46
8	89.96	92.65	93.52	90.25	93.59	96.58	95.82	94.35

Fig-5: In Vitro Drug Release of (F1-F8)

Formulations

All the three batches of formulation F6 were found to release the drug in 8 h. The cumulative percentage release was found to be 96.58 %.

Kinetic Modelling of Drug Release

All the Eight formulation of prepared matrix tablets of Etoposide were subjected to in-vitro release studies these studies were carried out using dissolution apparatus.

The results obtaining in vitro release studies were plotted in different model of data treatment as follows:

1. Cumulative percent drug released vs. time (zero order rate kinetics)
2. Log cumulative percent drug retained vs. time (First Order rate Kinetics)
3. Cumulative percent drug released vs. square root of time (Higuchi's Classical Diffusion Equation)
4. Log of cumulative % release Vs log time (Peppas Exponential Equation)

Table-5: Drug Release Kinetics of Formulation F6

TIME	%CDR	SQARE T	LOG T	LOG%CDR	ARA	LOG%ARA
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	15.11	1	0	1.17926446	84.89	1.92885653
2	25.98	1.41421356	0.30103	1.41463915	74.02	1.86934908
3	33.32	1.73205081	0.47712	1.52270499	66.68	1.82399559
4	49.78	2	0.60206	1.69705489	50.22	1.70087671
5	59.1	2.23606798	0.69897	1.77158748	40.9	1.61172331
6	65.98	2.44948974	0.77815	1.81941231	34.02	1.53173431
7	80.24	2.64575131	0.8451	1.90439092	19.76	1.29578694
8	96.58	2.82842712	0.90309	1.9848872	3.42	0.53402611

Zero Order Kinetics

Fig-6: Zero Order Kinetics of Optimized Formulation

First Order Kinetics

Fig-7: First Order Kinetics of Optimized Formulation

Higuchi Model

Fig-8: Higuchi Model of Optimized Formulation

Korsmeyer Peppas

Fig-9: Korsmeyer Peppas of Optimized Formulation

The values of in-vitro release were attempted to fit into various mathematical models. Plots of zero order, first order, Higuchi matrix and Peppas. Regression values are higher with Zero order release kinetics. Therefore all the Etoposide liposomes follow Zero order release kinetics. The table indicates that r^2 values are higher for Higuchi's model compared for all the liposomes.

Hence Etoposide release from all the liposomes followed diffusion rate controlled mechanism.

Stability Studies

There was no significant change in physical and chemical properties of the liposomes of formulation F-6 after 3 months. Parameters quantified at various time intervals were shown

Table- 6: Results of Stability Studies of Optimized Formulation F-6

Formulation Code	Parameters	Initial	1 st Month	2 nd Month	3 rd Month	Limits as per Specifications
F-6	25 ^o C/60%RH % Release	96.58	95.85	94.60	93.65	Not less than 85 %
F-6	30 ^o C/75% RH % Release	96.58	95.80	94.57	93.54	Not less than 85 %
F-6	40 ^o C/75% RH % Release	96.58	95.47	94.68	93.40	Not less than 85 %

CONCLUSION

From the performed work it was concluded that: Etoposide possesses all requisite qualities required for liposomal drug delivery. Among the various formulation, the combination F6 was found to be most suitable because of high encapsulation efficiency with smaller particle size. The formulation F6 comprising phosphatidylcholine, cholesterol fulfils the requirement of good liposomal formulation. In vitro drug release upto 8

h and more than 96.58 % drug released. Follows Peppas model in release studies. It shows encapsulation efficiency of 84.69 % and particle size of 80 μ m.

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